

Numerical Modelling of Thermoplastic Composite Fuselage Panels via Experimental Building Block Approach

Thomas Zaragkas¹, Spyridon Psarras¹, and Vassilis Kostopoulos¹

¹ Applied Mechanics Laboratory, Department of Mechanical Engineering and Aeronautics, University of Patras, Patras University Campus, GR-26504 Rio-Patras, Greece

Email: thomaszaragkas@upnet.gr, web page: <http://www.aml.mech.upatras.gr/en/home/>

Figure: Pyramid of Tests of Thermoplastic Composite Material-Indicative Photos of Tests and Simulations

NUMERICAL MODELLING & DAMAGE VERIFICATION

RESULTS & FUTURE WORK

- 1) Calibrated numerical models can forecast the experimental curves to a very good extend. Elastic, Fracture & Damage properties are obtained for further design. Though Hashin model in cases such as shear cannot reach the plasticity of LMPAEK matrix. A **one parameter-plasticity damage model** should be implemented in future.
- 2) There is a significant deviation between product and extracted properties mainly because of the different standard used. Specifically, the 10° off axis tension is expected to lead to higher elastic modulus against the $\pm 45^\circ$ shear experiment.
- 3) The component level design and verification is ongoing. In this level the interface of skin/stiffener and frame will be tested into compression and under Mode I for the adhesive interface properties to be extracted. Then the demonstrator stiffened panel will be submitted to compression and internal pressure.

REFERENCES

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